

She Deserves Better

A Poem by Kashish Gambhir

What do you call a man so emotionally crippled...
that the only way he builds bonds
is by mocking a woman's character?

This is how you recognize men deeply out of touch with real connection.
Men who've never had the capacity to honor —
the care of a sister,
the warmth of a mother,
or the genuine friendship of a woman.

These are the men who don't choose healing from their past,
They choose revenge.

And what does it tell about the men who laugh along?

Observe carefully —
notice who laughs and who doesn't.

Then you'll know exactly who these men are, on the inside.
And if you ever witness, or find yourself in a group like that —
where women's character is mocked just to bond...
because they can't create "real content" for conversation —
Muster the courage to stand for what's right.
And then walk away.

Because such men don't deserve the presence
of any woman in their lives.